

Role of Tourism in Economic Development: A Case Study of Koraput District of Odisha

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INTRODUCTION

Tourism and hospitality is an important parameter of socio-cultural identity and heritage of a country. In the era of globalization tourism and hospitality enhances the economic growth by job creation, source of foreign exchange and development of regions with potential for tourism. According to World Travel and Tourism Council (2014), the contribution of travel and tourism in world GDP is estimated to increase from 9.5% of GDP in 2013 to 10.3% of GDP in 2024 (WTTC, 2014). Tourism and hospitality industry contributes 6.8% of GDP of India, contributes 7.7% in total employment generated and provides foreign exchange of US\$18.13 billion. The tourism and hospitality sector is the third largest source of foreign exchange for India. The investment in tourism creates more jobs as compared to other sectors of economy. An investment of Rs. 10 lakh in tourism sector is estimated to create 89 jobs in hospitality industry as compared to 45 jobs in agriculture and 13 jobs in manufacturing sector (Planning Commission). Hotel industry generates revenues of US\$ 400-500 billion annually. In India tourism and hospitality has emerged as a sunrise industry with rise in number of foreign tourists.

Before COVID-19, travel and tourism had become one of the most important sectors in the world economy, accounting for 10 percent of global GDP and more than 320 million jobs worldwide. In 1950, at the dawn of the jet age, just 25 million people took foreign trips. By 2019, that number had reached 1.5 billion, and the travel and tourism sector had grown to almost too-big-to-fail proportions for many economies. The global pandemic, the first of its scale in a new era of interconnectedness, has put 100

million jobs at risk, many in micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises that employ a high share of women, who represent 54 percent of the tourism workforce, according to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Tourism-dependent countries will likely feel the negative impacts of the crisis for much longer than other economies. Contact-intensive services key to the tourism and travel sectors are disproportionately affected by the pandemic and will continue to struggle until people feel safe to travel en masse again. "There is no way we can grow our way out of this hole we are in," Irwin LaRocque, secretary-general of the Caribbean Community (CARICOM), said at a virtual event in September. From the white sand beaches of the Caribbean, Seychelles, Mauritius, and the Pacific to the back streets of Bangkok, to Africa's sweeping national parks, countries are grappling with how to lure back visitors while avoiding new outbreaks of infection. The solutions range from wooing the ultra rich who can quarantine on their yachts to inviting people to stay for periods of up to a year and work virtually while enjoying a tropical view. Tourism receipts worldwide are not expected to recover to 2019 levels until 2023. In the first half of this year, tourist arrivals fell globally by more than 65 percent, with a near halt since April—compared with 8 percent during the global financial crisis and 17 percent amid the SARS epidemic of 2003, according to ongoing IMF research on tourism in a post-pandemic world. The October *World Economic Outlook* projected the global economy would contract by 4.4 percent in 2020. The shock in tourism-dependent economies

will be far worse. Real GDP among African countries dependent on tourism will shrink by 12 percent. Among tourism-dependent Caribbean nations, the decline will also reach 12 percent. Pacific island nations such as Fiji could see real GDP shrink by a staggering 21 percent in 2020. The World Tourism and Travel Council in a report on the future of the industry said the pandemic has shifted travelers' focus to domestic trips or nature and outdoor destinations. Travel will largely be "kick started by the less risk averse travelers and early adopters, from adventure travelers and backpackers to surfers and mountain climbers," the report says.

Tourism is the largest industry in India and also globally and is considered as an economic bonanza. Huge potentials can be observed from various related segments of this industry. It is the only industry which has, with its immense opportunities attracted the attention of various groups towards it, directly or indirectly. Tourism has the ability to motivate human beings through its various sources; be it adventure, religious, wildlife, nature, sports, etc. Tourism is a service-based industry with hodge-podge of related industries as it can accelerate various developmental activities. It contributes to conservation of natural beauty, earning of revenue and also employment avenues. Now, the endeavor should be to boost tourism in India which in turn would act as a catalyst for the country's development. In fact, most of the countries around the world are turning to tourism as they consider it as one of the engines for economic development. Tourism in India has the potential of becoming one of the leading economies around the globe.

Classification of Tourism

Tourism may be broadly classified into two types:

1. Traditional Tourism
2. Niche Tourism

1. Traditional Tourism

In this form of tourism, generally, travelling is planned beforehand with the help of tour operators. Every information is being provided by the tour operators before the actual travel period starts. A large number of travelers are involved in this form of tourism which takes the form of social activity. The tourists mostly emphasize on sight-seeing, visit to various spots viz. heritage, pilgrim, wildlife etc. They are not interested in focusing on economical and cultural environment of the region.

2. Niche Tourism

Niche Tourism is a form of tourism in which small group of people is involved in travelling plan and which is being planned and decided spontaneously. Here, the traveler seeks to focus on local culture,

language and norms of the particular place of travel for the urge to acquire knowledge and experience about it. The tourists in this form, unlike traditional form, try to get involved in economical and cultural environment of the place of travel.

In this dissertation a humble attempt will be made to highlight the problems and prospects of the tourism industry in Koraput district of Odisha and the role of media for the development of these spots which will lead to the development of these destinations as well as it will be a boost for the development of the economy of the tribal stakeholders in general and that of the Economy of Odisha in Particular.

3. Objectives

The main objectives of the study are :-

1. To study the existing scenario of the tourism industry in Koraput District;
2. To assess the relation between media and tourism industry;
3. To identify the constraints, if any, which impede the promotional role of media;
4. To identify the innovative prospects put forward by both the tourism industry and the media.

Research Queries

The study has conducted with the following research queries-

1. Whether the existing scenario of the tourism industry in Koraput is contributing to the state's economy
2. Whether tourism industry is dependent on media for its development.
3. Whether the media always play the positive role in the process of development of tourism industry
4. Whether there is any scope for innovation in the tourism industry through the help of media.

Research Methodology

The collected data have been analyzed by using elementary statistical tools and techniques like diagrammatic and graphic representation of data, classification and tabulation of data. The research methodology adopted for this study has been designed keeping in mind the objectives concerned. The methodology incorporates the following:

- A. Area of the Study:
- B. Research Design:
- C. Sampling Plan:
- D. Method of data collection in case of primary data:
- E. Sources of secondary data:

Area of the Study

The 10 selected tourist spots of Koraput district has been selected on the basis of convenient sampling. The tourist spots selected by convenience sampling method are as follows:

1. Punjisil-Waterfall
2. Duduma- Waterfall
3. Gupteshwar- Lord Shiva Shrine
4. Deomali- Highest mountain peak of Odisha
5. Sabara Srikhetra- The Mythical Jagannath Temple
6. Rani Duduma- Waterfall
7. Putusil- Waterfall
8. Maliguda- Longest Railway Tunnel
9. Kechela- Picnic Spot
10. Galigabdar- Waterfall

Research Design

The present research study is both descriptive and quantitative. The study tries to focus on the present scenario of tourism industry in the District of Koraput. So far as this is concerned, the study is descriptive in nature. So far as the analysis of data by various elementary statistical tools and techniques as mentioned above is concerned, the study is quantitative. Thus the study is partly descriptive and partly quantitative.

Sampling Plan

The reports published about this tourism destination will be ascertained through questionnaires.

The Nine most circulated Odia dailies whose reports about these spots will be analysed and suggestive measures will be recommended.

1. The Sambad
2. The Samaja
3. The Dharitri
4. The Pragatibadi
5. The Anupam Bharat
6. The Khabara
7. The Prajatantra
8. The Samaya
9. The Nitidana

In case of the electronic media the reports of the following television channels about these spots will be ascertained and analysed. Those were:

1. OTV
2. KANAK NEWS
3. NEWS18 ODISHA

Methods of Data Collection in case of Primary Data

1. Interview Schedule for Visitors

By visiting the places, whoever be the visitors has been interviewed through the Interview Schedules.

2. Google Form

The views of the citizens of Koraput district has ascertained through close ended questionnaires.

3. Questionnaires for Media

Questionnaires has also distributed to media agencies to collect the existing report made by the print and electronics media about these tourist destinations

Sources of Secondary Data

The sources of secondary data are the various literatures, including books, journals, research papers, articles and the database of tourism preserved in various tourist spots in Koraput district. The sources also include the database preserved in the resorts and hotels, internet, journals, periodicals, brochures, pamphlets etc.

Tools For Data Analysis

Simple statistical tools like average, percentage, etc has been used to analyse the data collected and diagrams like Pie-chart, Bar-Diagram has also been used to present the analysis in graphical/ photo pictorial forms.

Scope

The scope of the study is limited to the selected tourist spots Koraput District, Odisha

Literature Review

A plethora of literature reveals the long-term influence of tourism on economic growth, known as the tourism-led growth hypothesis. It can act as a growth engine by contributing to GDP growth, job creation, and foreign exchange generation. In contrast, economic growth also positively impacts tourism development, as it favors tourism activities by developing facilities and infrastructures, such as transportation development, information and communication technology development, electronic money, hotels, restaurants, and other entertainment services and facilities.

Jeon (2020) initiated a study in Korea to investigate the association between macro and non-macro variables on tourism companies' stock performance. The study included monthly data from January 2001 to December 2018. The results revealed that variables such as oil prices, exchange rate, and industrial production have an adverse effect on tourism companies' stock prices, while the effects of tourism expenditure and consumer price index are positive and significant. The quantile regression also revealed the negative effect of non-macro determinants on tourism stock. He concluded that macro and non-macro variables are statistically asymmetric and highly correlated to tourism stock performance.

Khan (2020) tried to explore the role of tourism in boosting Italy's economic growth, where she stated that there is a robust causal effect among such variables as economic growth, number of tourist arrival, international tourism receipt, and international tourism expenditure. Further, she revealed bidirectional causation between economic growth and tourism growth and economic growth to tourist arrivals. However, she also found unidirectional causality between economic growth to tourism expenditure, tourism growth to tourism expenditure, and more interestingly, she found no causal association between tourist arrivals and tourism expenditure.

Chattopadhyay (2006) explained that Religious tourism generates revenue in a way as no other kind of tourism does. It has a distinct edge over other kinds of tourism due to the pull of huge crowds in the form of tourists. Pilgrim tourism to holy places (tirtha-yatra) is an ancient and continuing religious tradition of the Culture of Hindus. Here religion, as a cultural dimension, assumes the vital role and central focus of tourism in which the tourists (pilgrims) from all strata of the Hindus participate. In pilgrim tourism, the dimension of religion forms the basis of tourism of pilgrimage by offering the reward of purification of the soul and attainment of objectives related to the problems of mundane existence. Hindus from time immemorial were attracted to their numerous holy sites spread throughout India.

Ash and Turner (1976) argues that Tourism development also has some positive and negative upon cultural traditions, lifestyle, and environment of the local people. Tourism also causes decline in morality through unending pursuit of fun, sun and sex by the golden hordes of pleasure seekers in the vacation destinations thus increasing in prostitution, drug consumption etc. Degradation of natural environment in tourists receiving areas is another problem, which is directly proportionate to the tourists' intake.

Murphy (1990) in his book, "Tourism Community Approach" carried a more balanced assessment of the industry and its impacts; since it involves the interests of many groups within a given setting. The travel industry produces expectations, sells dreams and provides memories. The Tourist Industry is composed of variety of trades in goods and services. Primary travel trades in the tourist industry are; hotel industry, food and beverage industry, transport industry, travel industry. Whereas, secondary travel trades include; retail shops of souvenirs, antiques and gifts etc, Banks and financial institutions, hair dressers, laundries and

suppliers of goods and services for hoteliers, caterers and transport undertakings.

TIURIST DESTINATION OF KORAPUT: A REPORT

Punjisil-Waterfall

Punjisil Water Fall is situated at Punjisil Village. It is around 15 km from Damanjodi and 35-40 km from Koraput Town, a part of Lakshmipur Tehsil. It's is a natural water park. It attracts large numbers of tourists from far and near for enjoying natural beauty. Visitors can take bath along with his family here.

Duduma (Machkund)

The Majestic waterfall, popularly known as Matsya Tirtha of epic fame falls from a height of 175 mtrs. Set in the heart of a picturesque hill, Duduma 70 Kms. to the South of Jeypore and 88 Kms away from Koraput is a rocky outlet for the river Machkund, which flows through this rough Terrain. These falls, with a 165-mtrs drop, are known by the name Dudumafalls presumably in the absence of an adjacent village to name them after, as the word 'Duduma' itself means 'Waterfall'. Below the falls for five or six kilometers the river flows towards the south-west in a deep and a gloomy gorge, hemmed in on both sides by rock walls seven or eight hundred feet high into which it is impossible to descend except by the winch or the flight of steps of the Machkund Project. Rock-climbing enthusiasts can try reaching the base of the fall from the opposite side of the hill, a route tribals claim can be Terribly Strenuous. Three Kms away from the Duduma water fall, a small village called Onakadelli draws the attraction of foreign tourists to its weekly market day on Thursday where the Neolithic tribe Bonda come from inaccessible forest for marketing. It is 90 Kms away from Koraput. The fall is best seen from the top of the terrain but to get to the base of the waterfall you must descend downhill, which is risky at times. Also, a Lord Shiva temple is situated at the downhill where local villagers assembles during the annual "Shiva Ratri" festival. The fall surrounded with terrains and lush greenery makes it a perfect place for outing.

Gupteshwar- Lord Shiva Shrine

The cave Shrine of Gupteswar nestles on a lush green hill, 58KMS from Jeypore, and 80 Kms away from Koraput, amidst deep forest. The Cavernous interior of the Temple enshrines a huge 'lingam'. The cave is a multi Chambered wonder, Gupteswar is also Popularly known as Gupta Kedara. Shabari a rocky stream of great scenic beauty flows by Gupteswar. It is believed that Lord Rama during his banishment to forest passed through this region on his way to Panchabati in Dandaka-ranya. The heavily wooded valley all around is a heaven for the adventure loners.

Tucked amidst dense forest and River Sabari, a tributary of River Kolab, flowing on the other side, Gupteswar-the cave shrine of Lord Shiva situated on a lime stone hill is a famous pilgrim site and the biggest tourist puller of the district. Devotees in thousands from Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Telengana and Chhattisgarh throng to the cave temple, in the holy month of Sravana and on the annual Shiva Ratri festival. As the name sounds Gupteswar means "The Hidden God" and the main cave temple with a two meter height "linga" in it is surrounded by several other small caves. The place is also popularly known as "Gupta Kedar". It is said that a tribal hunter had discovered the "Linga" inside the cave. The place is believed to have close links between first- century AD poet Kalidas. Researchers say that the ramagiri hills, which encircles the cave shrine as been described in the poet's, literally work Meghaduta.

Tribals will be seen selling minor forest produces outselling minor forest produces outside the temple. It's not advisable for a night stay at Gupteswar and to return prior to sun-set.

Deomali- Highest mountain peak of Odisha

As the road bends from National Highway-26 at Kunduli, the topography begins to change. The route enters an undulating lush green terrain as after a drive of around 20 km's the serpentine road leads to Deomali, the highest peak of Odisha.

With above 1672 meter from minimum sea level of the eastern ghat of India, Deomali is the pride of Koraput. With misty clouds around you and cold breeze piercing your body, trekking at this highest peak will give you some of the memorable moment which one would love to treasure for life. While it will be enjoyable to walk to the summit, but one should be careful during the return journey as the track is quite slippery. Apart from outstanding contrast of trekking in the highest peak of Odisha, also, one can get an arresting view of the Deomali range of Hills and a peep at the tribal villages situated at the foothills of Deomali.

Sabara Srikhetra- The Mythical Jagannath Temple

situated at a height of 2,900 ft above the sea level, the district headquarters town of Koraput is also identified as "Sabara Srikhetra" for the Jagannath Temple whose construction was completed in the year 1978. Constructed on a hilltop, the temple is dedicated to "Lord Jagannath". The panoramic view of the town and its salubrious climate makes it an attractive health resort. The breath taking scenery brings heaven to earth.

Its halls and surrounding temples, which were constructed in a phased manner, are ornate and grand in their appearance. The temple is fascinating, especially for non-Hindus who couldn't enter the Jagannath temple in Puri normally referred as "Srikhetra". The Jagannath temple has a display of Gods of the different states of India. There's also a selection of local forms of rangoli, traditional patterns made with white and coloured powders on doorsteps. At the back of the temple is a series of apses containing statuettes of Jagannath in his various guises and costumes. One can climb steps to reach the temple or can directly take the vehicle to the parking area which is nearer to the temple. The tribal museum adjoining to it, projects the rare cultural heritage of the tribals of this region. The tribal museum behind the Jagannath Temple Koraput with collections of mineral samples, tribal costumes, hand woven clothes, musical instruments, caters to and educates the tourists about the culture and heritage of Koraput tribals.

Rani Duduma- Waterfall

Rani Duduma water fall, situated just a kilometre away from Nandapur, will leave you awestruck. The waters fall in steps, forms a pool and then again falls results in a truly stunning view.

What To Expect Inside

1. An amazing Cascade waterfall active throughout the year, with clear water.
2. About 3 Kilometer from Nandapur main market.
3. prominent falls, with 2 of them accessible for trekking.
4. You can climb up to the first fall, which is the best fall among three, but it is very risky.
5. The water remains throughout the year and it increases in monsoon season.
6. Taking a cool shower under the natural fall water is possible.
7. At The Starting point, a park is being developed.
8. From parking place its 1 km climbing steps and passing through the paddy fields and by side of the river.
9. Picnic points available with cooking space.
10. It's excellent for both family and bachelor picnic.
11. It can be easily accessed by hiring local transportation or public transport facilities.
12. No good hotels or lodges are available, the nearest will be Similiguda.
13. Best Time to Visit: October-February
14. Parking Fee: ₹20/- Per Vehicle/Hour
15. Nearest Railway Station: Jeypore (1hr 51min)
16. Nearest Town: Nandapur

17. Nearest Market Place: Semiliguda

18. Trip Type: Families, Couples and Friends

Putusil- Waterfall

In Koraput district, nature has spread its rainbow scarf. Thick stack of green paddy fields in the country with beautiful mountain garlands. The natural fountain emerges out of the heart of granary. It looks like the Queen of Nature is dressed up here to welcome guests.

This is, Talamali of Putsil, one of the main attractions of Koraput. The region has always been a tourist attraction. This is a familiar name for Ollywod movie directors. The environment here is by no means inferior to the natural beauty of Uttarakhand's Uti and Simla in Uttarakhand. It is located at 3,700 feet above sea level, a part of Deomali hill. Due to the lack of publicity, such an attractive tourist destination has not been able to reach to a larger mass. At the foot of the hill there are small numbers of tribal villages. They have grown a variety of crops on the heart of rocks. It's raining and it's cold It's always a place for attraction for everyone. Putsil, which flows at the foot of the hill, attracts tourists. Here many ollywood films like Rowdy Raja, Tu Mo Sathire, Nua Thikana, Love you Priya has been shoot here. It is situated in the Dudhari Panchayat of Semiliguda. Its situated around 37 kms from Koraput

Maliguda- Longest Railway Tunnel

A journey from Rayagada to Koraput by train is like a visit to a hill station. The crisp and cool breeze blowing through the window, clouds shuttling from one mountain to another through tunnels is an experience every person will remember. As the train chugs along the 173-km-long route in the district and covers as many as 38 tunnels at regular intervals, the whole stretch provides one of the most fascinating and enjoyable. India's highest broad gauge railway tunnel is situated at the small village of Malliguda, a favorite place for weekend picnic and to unwind from tiring urban life journeys. While coming across the 12 stations on its route, the train leapfrogs gorges and ravines lumbering over bridges. Small railway stations nestling between mountains will be witnessed along the route. The train snaking over the curves, entering the tunnels with smoke bellowing out provides a glorious picture. The tunnels have a depth of 60 meter, sharp curvatures up to five degrees and steep gradients.

Kechela- Picnic Spot

After travelling around 10 km in waterway Pondi ferry point near Koraput town one can discover himself at the enthralling

Kechala besides Kolab reservoir. There is a copper plate which reveals that the village had been granted to one Narasingha Mishra by the then Maharaja Krishna Dev on the occasion of the solar eclipse on September 24, 1620.

Jain relics found in the place speak volume of impact of Jainism in the area in the medieval period. A 30 feet high Jain temple with images of Thirthankars identified as Resavanath, Mahavir Jain, Ambika Devi, Jakhya and Jakhyani indicates that Kechana was a seat of Jainism. One has to hire a private motorboat to reach Kechala as the motor boat pressed to service by the tourism department is lying defunct.

Galigabdar- Waterfall

Poets described Galigabdar water fall as, "Who is ready to come, the water in the body of the stone. The flute of the Blue Hero will blossom as the cascade of love blows" Situated in the Kotia Tehsil, Pottangi block, Galigabdar attracts many of the tourist from far and near. Its situated 57 kms away from the district headquarter of Koraput. But now a day's lack of safety measures at the picturesque Galigabdar Rathabali waterfall in Koraput district has raised concern among tourists visiting the spot. Located 11 km away from Pottangi block headquarter on the foothills of Deomali, one can get a view of Galigabdar Rathabali's multiple drops from a distance. Water gushes down in several steps through a single rock and visitors can climb to the top of the rock to have a closer look at the fall. For its stunning landscape, the waterfall gets visitors round the year from both within the State and Andhra Pradesh. Due to good road communication, the waterfall is easily approachable from even Raipur and Andhra Pradesh and on an average, at least 200 tourists visit the waterfall during the peak season. However, there has been a rise in number of accidents at the spot in the absence of safety measures.

In the absence of guard wall or fences around the waterfall, people usually fall while climbing atop the rocky surface of the waterfall or while posing at the top of the fall to get a selfie.

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Result of interaction with Interview Schedule with Tourist Personel

In all of the tourist places, all total 197 respondents were interviewed. The data collected with the interaction are depicted through the following tables and pie-Chart/ diagram.

Table No-4.01-Gender Status of the Respondents	
Gender of the Respondents	Nos.
Male	121
Female	76
Total	197

Age Group

Age Group	Nos. of Respondents
0-25	36
25-40	57
40-60	15
60-70	10
70 & Above	52
Total	197

Status of Foreign Tourists

Place	Nos.
Within Asia	00
Outside Asia	07
Total	07

Nationality

Nationality	Nos.
Indian	189
Other National	08
Total	197

Status of Indigenous Tourists

Place	Nos.
Within Odisha	163
Outside Odisha	27
Total	190

Occupation

Occupation	Nos of Tourists
Service	33
Business	43
Retired	52
Student	38
Self Employed	23
Other	08
Total	197

Table No-4.08- Travel likings of the Respondents	
Question: How do you like to travel	Answer
In Group	66
With Family	110
Solo Traveller	21

Status of Frequent Travelers

Table No-4.07- Status of Frequent Travelers

Question	Yes	No
Are you a frequent traveler?	166	31

Travel likings of the Respondents

Table No-4.09-Rating scale of Punjisil(00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Punjisil	Security	05
2.		Infrastructure	03
3.		Scenic beauty	09
4.		Attraction	08
5.		Cleanliness	05
6.		Maintenance	07
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	01
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	NA
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	05

Table No-4.10-Rating scale of Duduma (00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Duduma	Security	05
2.		Infrastructure	03
3.		Scenic beauty	10
4.		Attraction	10
5.		Cleanliness	05
6.		Maintenance	07
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	01
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	08
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	07

Table No-4.11-Rating scale of Gupteshwar (00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Gupteshwar	Security	07
2.		Infrastructure	10
3.		Scenic beauty	09
4.		Attraction	07
5.		Cleanliness	10
6.		Maintenance	10
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	18
8.		Accessibility	10
9.		Cuisine	08
10.		Toilet	05
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	09
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	07

Table No-4.12-Rating scale of Deomali(00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Deomali	Security	03
2.		Infrastructure	05
3.		Scenic beauty	07
4.		Attraction	08
5.		Cleanliness	07
6.		Maintenance	05
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	05
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	07
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	08

Table No-4.13-Rating scale of Sabara Srikhetra(00-10)

SI No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Sabara Srikhetra	Security	10
2.		Infrastructure	10
3.		Scenic beauty	08
4.		Attraction	07
5.		Cleanliness	10
6.		Maintenance	10
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	10
8.		Accessibility	10
9.		Cuisine	10
10.		Toilet	10
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	10
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	10
13.		Internet Facilities	10
14.		Rates of Transport	10

Table No-4.14-Rating scale of Rani Duduma (00-10)

SI No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Rani Duduma	Security	06
2.		Infrastructure	05
3.		Scenic beauty	10
4.		Attraction	08
5.		Cleanliness	07
6.		Maintenance	05
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	08
8.		Accessibility	07
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	07
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	08
13.		Internet Facilities	07
14.		Rates of Transport	05

Table No-4.15-Rating scale of Putusil (00-10)

SI No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Putusil	Security	07
2.		Infrastructure	08
3.		Scenic beauty	10
4.		Attraction	09
5.		Cleanliness	05
6.		Maintenance	08
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	04
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	07
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	07

Table No-4.16-Rating scale of Maliguda (00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Maliguda	Security	05
2.		Infrastructure	03
3.		Scenic beauty	04
4.		Attraction	06
5.		Cleanliness	07
6.		Maintenance	05
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	07
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	06
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	06

Table No-4.17-Rating scale of Kechela (00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Kechela	Security	05
2.		Infrastructure	07
3.		Scenic beauty	08
4.		Attraction	06
5.		Cleanliness	07
6.		Maintenance	06
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	05
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	06
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	08

Table No-4.18-Rating scale of Galigabdar (00-10)

Sl No.	Name of the Place	Status of Facility	Rating
1.	Galigabdar	Security	07
2.		Infrastructure	06
3.		Scenic beauty	10
4.		Attraction	10
5.		Cleanliness	10
6.		Maintenance	07
7.		Rates of the Hotel Room	NA
8.		Accessibility	06
9.		Cuisine	NA
10.		Toilet	NA
11.		Behaviour of the local staff	NA
12.		ATM/Credit Card Facilities	NA
13.		Internet Facilities	NA
14.		Rates of Transport	07

Purpose of visit to the place

The purpose of the tourist behind the visit of the concerned places as described as under:-

- A. Leisure
- B. Religious Trip

- C. Conference
- D. Business Purpose
- E. Medical/Health Issues
- F. Adventure/ Sports
- G. Visiting friends/ Relatives
- H. Education/ Research
- I. Shopping
- J. Heritage Site

Frequency of visit to Koraput

Out of the 197 respondents, 131 were first time visitors, 47 were 2nd time visitors and 19 were visitors with multi times. This data has depicted through the following pie chart.

Table No-4.19-Frequency of Visit of Tourists

Category	Frequency
1st Time Visitor	131
2nd Time Visitor	47
Multiple time visitor	19

For the question, which source actually influenced you to go for a planned vacation, the response received, has interpreted through the following bar-diagram and table:-

Table No-4.20-Influencing factor behind visit to Koraput

Influence Category	Numbers
Friends/Relatives	122
Television	37
Radio	8
Newspaper/ Megazine	30

Feedback

Feedback were received from the respondents about their opinion regarding 2nd time visit & recommending friend about visit. The response has interpreted through the following table.

Table No-4.21-Feedback

Question		Response	
Would you like to visit Koraput again		Yes	180
		No	17
Question		Response	
Will you recommend your friend to visit Koraput?		Yes	190
		No	07

Result of interaction with Questionnaire with Print & Electronic Media

Questionnaires were sent to the leading 10 Odia dailies, and their response is depicted through the following table.

Table No.4.22-Numbers of report published in Print Media about the study areas from 2011-2021

Name of the media Name of the tourist spot		The Sambad	The Samaja	The Dharitri	The Pragatibadi	The Anupam Bharat	The Khabara	The Prajatantra	The Samaya	The Nitidana
		1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.
1.	Punjisil	03	01	01	00	01	02	01	01	01
2.	Duduma	05	03	02	02	01	01	02	02	01
3.	Gupteshwar	08	04	03	02	01	02	01	03	01
4.	Deomali	10	05	03	02	01	01	01	01	01
5.	Sabara Srikhetra	12	05	01	01	02	04	05	03	01
6.	Rani Duduma	07	06	03	02	04	01	02	03	01
7.	Putusil	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
8.	Maliguda	03	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
9.	Kechela	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
10.	Galigabdar	03	02	01	01	01	01	01	01	01

The data of the publication of the reports about the selected tourist spots in print medias are as under:-

It depicts that the news paper The Sambad has largest nos. of publication about the these tourist spots. By reading these kinds o reports the tourists from far and near comes to enjoy the beauty of these tourist spots.

Questionnaires were sent to the leading 03 Odia Electronic Medias, and their response is depicted through the following table.

Table No.4.23 Numbers of reports broadcasted in Electronic Media about the study areas From 2011-2021

Name of the media →		OTV	KANAK NEWS	NEWS18 ODISHA
Name of The Tourist Spot ↓		1.	2.	3.
1.	Punjisil	01	01	01
2.	Duduma	03	02	01
3.	Gupteshwar	08	04	02
4.	Deomali	10	05	03
5.	Sabara Srikhetra	03	02	01
6.	Rani Duduma	05	06	02
7.	Putusil	02	01	02
8.	Maliguda	01	01	01
9.	Kechela	03	01	00
10.	Galigabdar	01	01	00

The data of the publication of the reports about the selected tourist spots in selected electronic medias are as under:-

It depicts that the news paper OTV has largest nos. of broadcasting about these tourist spots. By reading these kinds o reports the tourists from far and near comes to enjoy the beauty of these tourist spots.

MAJOR FINDINGS

The findings have been presented below in accordance with the attributes:

A. Safety and security

It is the first attribute studied and it was found that tourists from within India/ Odisha and outside Asia were highly satisfied with safety and security matter when it came to expectations. The expectations might have been created through information search through various means

B. Infrastructure

When the researcher studied the satisfaction level in terms of infrastructure, it was found that the tourists were not highly satisfied after their travel experience

in Koraput though their expectations were very high before their travel.

C. Scenic Beauty

When the researcher studied the satisfaction level with respect to Scenic Beauty, it was found that tourists were not highly satisfied after their travel experience in Koraput, even if their expectations were very high before their travel.

D. Attraction

When the researcher studied the satisfaction level in terms of Attraction, it was found that tourists were not highly satisfied after their travel experience in Koraput though their expectations were very high before their travel.

E. Cleanliness

Nowadays, cleanliness of every spot is an important aspect for every traveler. Since, tourists travel in groups, family and friends, hygiene is always a matter of concern for them. In this study, the researcher found that the tourists were highly satisfied with their experiences in terms of cleanliness of the surrounding, in spite of their expectations which was comparatively less.

F. Maintenance

The tourists were highly satisfied with their experiences in terms maintenance of the entire requirements needed in tourism industry. Maintenance of surrounding, ambience, infrastructure, and other related services.

G. Behavior of local staff

Many people are associated with the tourism sector in one or the other way. Staff of railways, airways, hotels, hospitals, resorts, lodges, etc. including the gatekeeper has an important role to play when it comes to delivering of services to the tourists. It always creates a huge impact in tourist experience during their tour.

H. Accessibility

It is also an important factor for the tourists during their travel plan which they focus upon. The researcher found that every tourist in this study was highly satisfied in terms of accessibility in their expectation and experience level which was same before and after their travel.

I. Cuisine

Cuisine of a place is always a unique experience for the tourists which they want to explore. Ethnic food is always a source of attraction for the tourists towards a place. In case of Local Cuisines of Koraput, the expectation of the tourists was high but after their experiences, they seem to be not highly satisfied.

J. ATM/Credit Card

This facility is always looked upon by the tourists since it is quite risky to carry cash in the entire journey. Their expectation in this regard was not high during their visit to Koraput, but their experiences were very good and they were highly satisfied when it came to ATM/Credit facility. But in the concerned tourist places, there is no such ATMs, but it is situated in the nearby town, which 20-30 kms distance.

K. Toilet

The expectation of the tourist towards Koraput in terms of toilet is not good as in 80% of the areas there is no such official toilet facility.

L. Information/Communication

In terms of Information and Communication, the tourists were of the assumption that the internet facility, wireless communication, cell phones and communication means will not be satisfactory which is partially correct.

M. Rates of hotels/transport

The tourists had high expectations in terms of rates of hotels and transport but after their visit to Koraput their experiences were not highly satisfactory.

Suggestions

This is the final stage of the thesis where the Researcher proposes to put forward the following suggestions for different stakeholders. Such suggestions will definitely act as eye openers to the policy makers, entrepreneurs, tourists, tour operators etc.

1. State Tourism Department should first try to understand the loopholes which hinder the tourism growth and then try to frame the necessary steps to remove the loopholes and put extra efforts to develop the tourism scenario of Koraput.
2. **Festivals** that are being arranged in different times, can be a good source for promotion of Tourism Industry. For example, Spring festival of China expects rush of travelers and even in the ticket booths, people wait for hours for purchase; the same trend can also be created in Odisha through festivals.
3. **Conducive and friendly atmosphere** for tourists is of utmost importance. Goa is being ranked in the top 10 nightlife cities list by "National Geographic", it is getting recognized in the global platform for being the safe destination. This is exemplary news for many States. Since, in today's world of turmoil and chaos, people are scared to plan for a trip even though they are financially sound or free to move from place to place. Safety and security is the most important concern for every tourist. Hence, if the atmosphere of Odisha can be focused or promoted properly as being the place for tourism rather than the place of terrorism, with proper security in all spots, then definitely innumerable travelers will flow towards Odisha. It is necessary to work for law and order situations and safety and security measures before promoting Koraput as a perfect place for tourists.
4. Government initiative should be to work for creation of proper image of a destination, which has huge potential for Tourism industry to grow and develop. Allocation of promotional funds by the State Tourism Department can efficiently

and effectively help the tourism sector to mark a position in global map. Website information plays an important role for promotion of Koraput Tourism. Therefore, up to date and proper information should be provided in the websites.

5. Media is still failing to provide a proper picture of Odisha at the national scenario, forget about global. Hence, abolishing such important heritage of Odisha cum Koraput is itself a need of discussion of the hour and since print media can play an important role to bring tremendous change through such news it should strategize their responsibility and revolutionize the modern tourism.
6. Media is a strong weapon whose effective use is the need of the hour for the larger interests of Odisha. Youths of Odisha cum Koraput should not use the social media for creating turmoil in State but to showcase the issues in a much logical manner so that their own state does not face any depressing situation in global scenario. At this juncture, the contribution of media and society should be such that Odisha is framed as a constructive state for revenue earning, employment generation and better connectivity to rest of the world. This will bring revolution to tourism industry of Odisha.
7. The tourist guides should be properly trained so that they can properly interact with the tourists specially the foreign tourists. They should be provided a device which can be used as a translator so that it does not become difficult for them to communicate.
8. Films can also be a good source for promotion of Koraputia Culture. Since, through films, the visuals of different spots, scenic beauty, landscapes, and various information can be highlighted.
9. Air, road and rail connectivity need to be developed and upgraded for a region to succeed in the present competitive and fast world. For this particular development adequate investment is a must so that it can help in boosting tourism sector in a way too.
10. The Government should take initiatives to help the local youths in promoting healthy food, the organic and herbs related food items. This can effectively proceed a long way to boost the tourism industry of Odisha cum Koraput.

The Tourism Industry should also work on including, developing and also modifying the prioritized factors

so that the region can expect more tourist inflow round the year.

CONCLUSION

The Tourism industry, in recent times, is the booming industry. Every country nowadays puts extra effort to grow and develop the Tourism Industry, since it helps in generating revenue, employment and also earn foreign exchange to a large extent. It is the only industry which holistically helps the associated sectors to develop along with it. The Tourism Industry is the generator for economic development of the country as a whole. The developed countries have worked for the promotion of tourism industry by bringing a paradigm shift to the local culture, traditions and conserving the natural beauty in spite of fast development. But the scenario of developing countries in terms of tourism promotion still needs much more effective strategy to move forward. As tourism industry is the visual industry, every product and service designed for it to offer, needs to be displayed through media to the entire world. Most parts of the globe are still not known to the general public. Awareness of existence of a region or products or services can only be created through a proper medium, and media is the strong weapon which can create and even destroy an image of the entire system. Therefore, Media can be effectively and efficiently used to promote the tourism industry of a region which will directly contribute to socio-economic change.

When the taste and preferences of the Tourists are understood, it becomes easy for the concerned department to take necessary steps to work for the development or modifications of the required aspects which will contribute to tourism development of the region. Media has a tremendously important role to play for the development of the tourism industry, provided the minimum requirements considered important for tourism development is looked into for proper maintenance and growth. Innovation is seen in recent times in tourism industry in order to be competitively successful in global platform. New techniques, new products, new services, new methods and new places are being designed and explored to make the entire globe aware about Odisha and Koraputia Culture. The role of media in generating interest for choosing Koraput as its travel destination cannot be overlooked. It is extremely indispensable for the development of the tourism industry in the state. Media is, in fact, a mirror which reflects the picture of the society which is essential for tourism industry. A judicious and prudent use of media will definitely open a new horizon in this non-smoke industry.

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